

Report outlining a strategic approach for efficiency savings based on concurrency and accuracy

Deliverable D2.6

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

Earth System Models typically comprise a number of component models such as an atmospheric model, ocean model, ice model and a chemistry model. These execute as separate executables or as a single executable and exchange data using a coupler. The coupler controls the execution and time evolution of the complete system by synchronising and controlling the flow of data between the various components. In this work we explore the use of OpenMP to run model components concurrently within a single executable. The model components supported here are the ECMWF radiation and wave models. To run concurrently with the rest of the IFS forecast model, it is necessary that these components run lagged by one radiation time-step and one model time-step respectively. The objective is to improve the computational performance beyond what is achieved today whether component models are run sequentially or concurrently using a single executable or separate executables.

2. Conclusion & Results

The comodels OpenMP approach was successfully implemented for the IFS forecast model with the radiation scheme and wave model as the two comodels. This configuration produced bit identical results when the number of MPI tasks was changed and the number of threads assigned to the model core or comodels was changed.

The results show that there is clearly the potential to improve scalability using comodels but this appears to be conditional on having one or more component models that by themselves scale poorly. Given the significant technical effort that was required for the implementation, the performance gain from the use of co-models was rather limited. However, it may be possible to get better results on architectures that use more threads in parallel or if model parts can be separated that are more expensive in comparison to the rest of the model.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
Improve the efficiency and productivity of numerical weather and climate simulation on high-performance computing platforms	Yes
Support the end-to-end workflow of global Earth system modelling for weather and climate simulation in high performance computing environments	Yes
The European weather and climate science community will drive the governance structure that defines the services to be provided by ESIWACE	No
Foster the interaction between industry and the weather and climate community on the exploitation of high-end computing systems, application codes and services.	Yes
Increase competitiveness and growth of the European HPC industry	No

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Provide services to the user community that will impact beyond the lifetime of the project.	Yes

Improve scalability and shorten the time-to-solution for climate and operational weather forecasts at increased resolution and complexity to be run on future extreme-scale HPC systems.	Yes
Foster usability of the available tools, software, computing and data handling infrastructures.	Yes
Pursue exploitability of climate and weather model results.	No
Establish governance of common software management to avoid unnecessary and redundant development and to deliver the best available solutions to the user community.	No
Provide open access to research results and open source software at international level.	Yes
Exploit synergies with other relevant activities and projects and also with the global weather and climate community	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

It was the aim of ESIWACE WP2 to investigate the possibility of de-sequencing and thus enhancing concurrency between parts of the model as well as the use of single precision in model simulations to increase performance. Work on single precision has been summarized in the IFS high resolution demonstrator deliverable D2.8. This report is now summarising results from the study of comodels within the IFS model. The work is focusing on the execution of the radiation scheme and the wave model in parallel to the rest of the model. Both of these components run today within a single IFS executable and are initiated by a subroutine call, running sequentially with the rest of the IFS model. Within the EU funded CRESTA project we explored running the radiation scheme concurrently (using separate MPI tasks) with the rest of the model the outcome of this work was summarised in *Mozdzyński and Morcrette, 2014*. In this work we found that it was only beneficial to run the radiation scheme concurrently with the rest of the model if it was run at every model time-step which was an unrealistic configuration due to the high cost of the radiation computations. A second problem was the relatively high cost of exchanging data using MPI from the IFS model to the radiation scheme and returning data from the radiation scheme to the IFS model. With the OpenMP comodels approach, the radiation scheme also runs concurrently with the IFS model. However, as the radiation scheme runs on the same MPI tasks as the IFS model there is no additional MPI communication needed between the model and the radiation scheme.

In Figure 1 we show the generic structure of the comodels approach, where a number of comodels all run concurrently with the IFS model core. To run concurrently it is necessary for all comodels to run in a lagged mode by using data from an earlier time-step. As each comodel and the model core use their own subset of the total tasks' threads (OMP_NUM_THREADS) it is important that the data they use is thread-safe. By this we mean that in their execution there is no write-read conflict which is a typical constraint for all OpenMP Parallel Regions. If there is a conflict then this must be resolved by adding synchronisation between the model core and the corresponding comodel. An example of such a synchronisation occurs in the model core when it calls UPDTIM from CNT4. Depending on the updated date and time climatology fields are updated which are accessed in the radiation scheme. In this case the synchronisation should only take place if the model core has reached a radiation time-step.

Figure 1: The generic structure of comodels.

In the development of the synchronisation code we found it extremely useful to include the code location where the synchronisation calls are made. With this information being available this location would be printed out as a diagnostic if the synchronisation delay is excessive and even abort at a greater threshold. Further it was useful to include calls to the IFS gstats timer package at the synchronisation locations which would allow us to understand the real cost of any synchronisation used. Ideally the synchronisation cost should be negligible, but this is dependent on the number of threads assigned to the model core and individual comodels.

In Figure 2 we show a schematic for the comodels implementation where we have assigned 13 threads to the model core, 3 threads to the radiation scheme and 2 threads to the wave model. The number of threads to use is set in a namelist variable for each comodel, and the remainder up to `OMP_NUM_THREADS` is given to the model core. In other namelist variables we can specify whether a component model should run sequentially or as a comodel. If we specify all component models to run sequentially then the model results match the control experiment as no component model needs to run in a lagged mode. The exact number of threads to assign to each comodel is determined by doing a number of runs and inspecting the IFS gstats counters printed at the end of model execution. A starting point for the thread distribution could be to set the number of threads in proportion to the wall clock cost observed for each component model in a control experiment. This is a reasonable strategy however it assumes the cost is dominated by computations. Even if this were the case then adjusting the thread number by just one thread would have the effect on performance (positive or negative) of 1/18 or about 5 percent assuming we are using 18 threads per task. This is a relatively high overhead. Of course, on a future architecture with hundreds of threads per task this would be less of an issue. For this work, default binding was used on the ECMWF XC-40 CRAY systems (4 tasks with 18 threads per task being contained on each node).

Figure 2: IFS implementation with radiation and wave model (WAM) component comodels.

In Figure 3 we show the performance of an IFS 9 km (TCo1279¹) forecast model comparing the performance of control and comodel runs on one of ECMWF's CRAY XC-40 clusters. Performance is measured in forecast days per day (FD/D), where the operational requirement is 240 FD/D, which is a 10 day forecast in one hour. We observe that the performance of the comodel runs is better than the control, however, scaling is only up to 1024 nodes. We also noticed that the best performance for comodel runs occurred when only 1 or 2 threads were assigned to the wave model, the remaining threads being given to the model core and radiation as shown in Table 1.

XC-40 nodes	model core	radiation	WAM
256	11	5	2
512	13	4	1
1024	12	4	2
2048	13	4	1

Table 1: TCo1279 comodel thread distribution.

¹ The term TCoNNNN refers to the IFS spectral model naming convention employing a cubic-octahedral grid (TCo) with a wavenumber truncation at NNNN

Figure 3: TCo1279 9 km (9 km horizontal resolution) IFS forecast model comparing control and comodel runs.

FORECAST DAYS PER DAY					
XC-40 NODES	control	comodels	Speedup %	Control radiation %	Control WAM %
256	303.2	309.1	1.9	10.9	7.4
512	497.9	524.8	5.4	9.4	10.1
1024	695.9	789.2	13.4	7.6	20.8
2048	603.4	742.8	23.1	3.3	46.9

Table 2: TCo1279 Forecast Model performance.

In Table 2 we observe that the control cost of the wave model (WAM) did not scale. The problem was identified in the message passing code used to communicate the diagnostic global norms for three 2-D fields (Charnock, U-Stokes, V-Stokes) to the master task. The logic used was a non-blocking MPI-Send from each task and a corresponding blocking MPI-Recv on the master task. When this logic was recoded as a collective MPI_gatherv, the severe overhead no longer existed. This fix has been submitted for inclusion in the IFS code repository. One can ask why this problem was not identified sooner. The reason is that at 364 XC-40 nodes (the number of nodes used for operations for the TCo1279 forecast model) the poor scaling of the wave model simply was not evident. The performance of the TCo1279 forecast model comparing runs of the control against just the wave model fix (wamfix) is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: TCo1279 IFS forecast model – improving wave model scaling.

Figure 5 compares the performance of runs with the new control (with the wave model fix) and comodels also with the wave model fix included. We observe that there is a marginal performance improvement up to 1024 nodes and a reduction in performance at 2048 nodes.

Figure 5: TCo1279 9 km IFS forecast model with wamfix for both control and comodel runs.

Finally, for comodels to run concurrently this requires component models to run in a lagged mode meaning data is used from a previous time-step. For the radiation scheme this means one earlier radiation time-step which can be one or more model time-steps, while for the wave model this is one earlier model time-step. For the TCo1279 model case we ran with a default model time-step of 450 secs and radiation frequency of 1800 secs. This meant that the model would have 4 model time-steps to execute during which the radiation scheme would execute once. With the lagged mode of execution synchronisation is required in the initial time-steps as data is required from the first time-step to also start the second model (for wave model) and radiation time-steps. Naturally the lagged mode results in small differences in results compared to the control where component models are run sequentially. These differences were found to be insignificant in the study for the task-based radiation in parallel scheme reported in *Mozdzynski and Morcrette, 2014*.

5. References (*Bibliography*)

Mozdzynski, G, Morcrette J, March 2014, ECMWF Technical Memorandum 721, Reorganization of the Radiation Transfer Calculations in the ECMWF IFS
<https://www.ecmwf.int/en/elibrary/11300-reorganization-radiation-transfer-calculations-ecmwf-ifs>

Mogensen, K, Keeley, S, Towers, P, April 2012, ECMWF Technical Memorandum 673, Coupling of the NEMO and IFS models in a single executable,
<https://www.ecmwf.int/en/elibrary/11175-coupling-nemo-and-ifs-models-single-executable>

6. Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Dissemination

The results of this study have been presented at PASC18 Platform for Advanced Scientific Computing Conference, Basel, July 2-4, 2018

6.2 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable:

X	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

7. The delivery is delayed: Yes No

8. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

None

9. Sustainability

9.1. Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date

Comodels have the potential to improve scalability but this appears to be conditional on having one or more component models that by themselves scale poorly for whatever reason, I/O, OpenMP, message passing to name a few.

We suspect it may be better to focus efforts to resolve such scaling problems without pursuing a comodels approach.

Is 18 threads per MPI task too small? Possibly, but today's distributed memory architectures for standard CPU hardware do not support hundreds of threads per MPI task where comodels potentially could improve scalability. However, this may be different if hardware such as Intel's Knights Landing is used that can support a very large number of threads.

Debugging comodels could be problematic. In any program using OpenMP finding bugs in OpenMP parallel regions is never easy especially if they occur infrequently or result in small differences. At ECMWF, we demand that IFS applications produce bit identical results on repeated runs. Commenting out OpenMP parallel directives in recently modified code areas can give a clue to localise a bug. However, with comodels component models use OpenMP to run in parallel with each other and this makes finding bugs increasingly harder to locate. Of course, we can always run a component model sequentially to aid debugging.

Comodels require synchronisation to control access to data that is shared and is updated by the model core or a comodel. Such programming is never easy and is potentially difficult for scientists that have only experience of sequential programming. Adding timers around code areas where synchronisation had been applied is a useful approach to understand the cost of synchronisation. Likewise, it is useful to have debug prints to STDERR in the synchronisation call interface that report the code location on excessive synchronisation delays or abort on reaching some maximum delay. The objective is to avoid wasting computer resources when adding some incorrect synchronisation and to provide a useful diagnostic where the application is hanging in this situation.

10. Dissemination activities

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Location , dates	Type of audience reached In the context of all dissemination & communication activities ('multiple choices' is possible)	Estimated number of persons reached
Participation to a conference	Talk at Platform for Advanced Scientific Computing 2018 PASC 2018 (https://pasc18.pasc-conference.org/).	Basel (CH), Switzerland, 2-4 July 2018	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	50

Organisation of a workshop	Minisymposium at PASC 2018 No. 1: Title: Towards Weather and Climate Simulations at 1km Resolution Convener: Peter Dueben; Co-convener: Carlos Osuna	Basel (CH), Switzerland, 2-4 July 2018	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	50
Organisation of a workshop	Minisymposium at PASC 2018 No. 2: Title: Machine Learning in Weather and Climate Convener: Peter Dueben; Co-convener: Rupert Ford and Willem Deconinck	Basel (CH), Switzerland, 2-4 July 2018	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	50
Organisation of a workshop	Minisymposium at PASC 2018 No. 3: Title: How to Escape the Data Avalanche in Climate Science? Convener: Oliver Fuhrer; Co-convener: Joachim Biercamp	Basel (CH), Switzerland, 2-4 July 2018	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	50

Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

Type of IP Rights	Application reference	Date of the application	Official title of the application	Applicant(s)	Has the IPR protection been awarded?	If available, official publication number of award of protection
None						

None